

WELCOME to the first newsletter for the Urban Surface Energy Balance: Land Surface Scheme Model Comparison Project. We plan to send an updated newsletter monthly through the course of this work providing updates on progress and initial findings. Please circulate this issue to any relevant and interested parties.

Project Summary

There has been a rapid increase in the number of land-atmosphere exchange models which explicitly parameterize urban surfaces. These models have been developed for a wide range of purposes including improved weather forecasting, climate predictions, air quality forecasting and assessment of the impact of mitigation strategies.

Given the number of models available, our objective is to investigate questions including (although not limited to):

- do these models produce physically realistic simulations of urban heat exchange?
- how do the models perform in terms of cost (computer time and data requirements) and benefit (improved model prediction)?
- how complex do parameterizations of heat exchange need to be to obtain accurate results?

The methodology to be adopted will be similar to that used in PILPS, the Project for Inter-comparison of Land-Surface Parameterization Schemes (*Henderson-Sellers et al. 1993*). This involves a four stage approach:

1. Participants will be provided with forcing data only. No information will be provided regarding the urban surface from which this evaluation dataset was taken. Therefore models will be run based on the 'urban' parameters.
2. Morphological data of the urban environment in question will be provided, including data concerning building density, mean building height and vegetation cover.
3. Details of the urban fabric will be provided in terms of thermal properties, surface cover fraction and albedo. This information is specific to each city and is not generally known on a global basis.

4. The full evaluation dataset will be released to participants to allow for optimisation of the model parameters to best fit the observations. At this stage, modelling groups will also return information on their optimised parameters as well as the standard outputs retrieved.

The models are to be run *offline* so that the forcing data are provided for the 'top' of the land-surface scheme and so there is no feedback to larger scale conditions within the modelling domain.

Current Status

- Table 1 lists the participants who have indicated that they will participate, along with the urban land surface scheme models they will use. Note that this list is subject to change as we engage other participants and/or if models are found to be unsuitable for any reason.
- A paper has been prepared that summarizes the characteristics of the models involved up to now:
http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm
- An initial assessment of these models has commenced in terms of examining the data they require as input and the data they produce as output.
- To ensure data compatibility each group has been provided with a data set which was originally in the netCDF format – a standard among many modellers. However, it appears that many groups do not use this format. **We need each group to run their model(s) with the specimen data and for them to return their output to us.**
- We are currently reviewing the meteorological data to be used (the evaluation dataset) for input.
- Regular updates can be found at our website:
http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

It is not too late to become involved in this work. Please contact us as soon as possible if you are interested or plan in participating.
UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk

Table 1: Model and groups that will participate

MODEL NAME	CODE	PARTICIPANTS
Building Effect Parameterization	BEP02	<i>Alberto Martilli, CIEMAT, Spain</i>
Building Effect Parameterization	BEP05	<i>Rafiq Hamdi, Royal Observatory of Belgium</i>
Canyon Air Temperature	CAT	<i>E Erell Ben Gurion University, Israel</i> <i>T Williamson University of Adelaide, Australia</i>
Community Land Model - Urban	CLMU	<i>Keith Oleson, NCAR, USA</i>
Environmental Meteorology Model	ENVimet	<i>Michael Bruse, University of Bochum, Germany</i>
Green Cluster Thermal Time Constant model	GCTTC	<i>Limor Shashua-Bar, Institute of Technology, Israel</i>
Joint UK Land Environment Scheme 1 Tile	JULES1T	<i>Aurore Porson, University of Reading, UK</i>
Joint UK Land Environment Scheme 2 Tile	JULES 2T	<i>Aurore Porson, University of Reading, UK</i>
Joint UK Land Environment Scheme Urban	JULESU	<i>Aurore Porson, University of Reading, UK</i>
Local-scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme	LUMPS	<i>Sue Grimmond, King's College London, UK</i>
Microscale Urban Climate Model	MUKLIMO	<i>Uwe Sievers, Deutscher Wetterdienst, Germany</i>
MM5- urbanized	MM5u	<i>M Trombou, A Dandou, University of Athens, Greece</i>
Multi-layer Urban Canopy Model	MUCM	<i>H Kondo National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan</i>
Noah land surface model/Single-layer Urban Canopy Model	NSLUCM	<i>Fei Chen, NCAR, USA</i>
Reading Urban Model	RUM	<i>Aurore Porson, University of Reading</i>
Simple Urban Energy Balance Model for Meso-Scale Simulation	SUMM	<i>Manabu Kanda, Toru Kawai, Ryo Moriwaki, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>
Simple Urban Neighbourhood Boundary Energy Exchange Model	SUNBEEM	<i>John Arnfield, Ohio State University, USA</i>
Slab Urban Energy Balance Model	SUEB	<i>K Fortuniak, University of Lodz, Poland,</i>
Soil Model for Submesoscales, Urbanized	SM2U	<i>Isabelle Calmet, Ecole Centrale de Nantes, France</i>
Temperature of Urban Facets in 3D	TUF3D	<i>Scott Krayenhoff, UBC, James Voogt UW, Canada</i>
Temperatures of Urban Facets in 2D	TUF2D	<i>Scott Krayenhoff, UBC, James Voogt UW, Canada</i>
Town Energy Balance	TEB	<i>V Masson, CNRM, France</i>
Town Energy Balance 07	TEB07	<i>Rafiq Hamdi, Royal Observatory of Belgium</i>
Urban Canopy Layer Model	UCLM	<i>Gerald Mills, UC Dublin, Ireland</i>
Urbanised version of DMI-HIRLAM model	HIRLAM-U	<i>A Baklanov, Danish Meteorological Institute, Denmark</i>
Vegetated Urban Canopy Model	VUCM	<i>Jong-Jin Baik, SH Lee, Seoul National University, South Korea</i>

Next steps

- We are still keen to get more participants. If you want to know of a group that is not currently participating but that you think would be interested, please forward them this newsletter.
- It is important that all groups successfully run the specimen data set. We will provide participants with this data either in the netCDF or ASCII format. Target Date: Mar 1 2008

Further Information

If you have any queries or want to get involved, please contact us: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk
http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

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Funding provided by

